

Mediating Role Of Organization Culture Between Knowledge Management Practices And Employee Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 09, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Knowledge Management Practices, Organization Culture, Employee Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5173001</p>	<p><i>In some last decades, Knowledge Management (KM) has advanced from a rising idea to an inexorably regular capacity in business associations. It is an open mystery that banking has changed over into the matter of data from the financial matters. The instability of worldwide business condition constrained and drove the banks to receive Knowledge Management (KM) Practices is the best tool to execute the performance building. KM is similarly essential and significant for banks all things considered for different establishments and associations. But there is thirst in literature to have research on knowledge management practices and its significance in improving the employee performance of banking sector. Despite of several studies to find the relationship between KM practices and employee performance, very little concentration has been given to develop the mediating mechanism of organization culture model which is called as CVF model. I have used CVF model as theoretical lens for this lens, because this model is never be testify to determine the relationship between KM practices and employee performance. The CVF model is a prominent and most widely used model in respect of organizational culture research literature inquires about because of its unwavering quality and viability. The data is collected through online survey from employees of banking sector and sample includes of employees from all the provinces of Pakistan. A total number of 480 questionnaires were distributed among employees and 430 takes into consideration for research analysis. On the basis of literature review and conceptual model total 32 hypotheses were developed and tested through mediation analysis and for whole data analysis PLS SEM 3.23 were used. The finding of this research has sound contribution in theoretical literature and practical implication as the organization culture has significant mediation between KM practices and employee performance.</i></p>

Introduction

In some last decades, Knowledge Management (KM) has advanced from a rising idea to an inexorably regular capacity in business associations. It is an open mystery that banking has changed over into the matter of data from the financial matters. The instability of worldwide business condition constrained and drove the banks to receive Knowledge Management (KM) Practices is the best tool to execute the performance building. KM is similarly essential and significant for banks all things considered for different establishments and associations. But there is thirst in literature to have research on knowledge management practices and its significance in improving the employee performance of banking sector.

Worker execution is the best criteria for evaluating representative against their viability in the organization (Mansori, Yazid and Khatibi, 2018). The main hurdle in the basic workforce and the executive's is Knowledge difficulties of the contemporary time. Henceforth increasingly focused associations are the individuals who adjust their hierarchical conduct to substances of the current workplace. The world itself is always moving with the end goal that organizations of various types need to adjust to outer and inner changes for their own survival (Hemamalini, 2014). As such, to endure and thrive in today's worldwide economy, the idea of the representative exhibition is imperative to numerous associations and foundations. According to Armstrong 2012, the employee performance is typically based on gender, and their conduct to work and progress on knowledge. Keney (2015) numerous associations have seen the need to put resources into the representative's presentation to improve their proficiencies; this will prompt more noteworthy returns. Representative execution is capable of to show progress within organization culture, simplicity in utilize the emerging innovation and profoundly active specialists and Sobia, Afsahan, Kamaran and Naser, (2012) and Keney (2015), articulated that the employee performance is expected against the presentation models set by the organization. There are different expectations that can be thought about when expecting performance, for example, utilization of profitability, efficiency, viability, quality and profit measures Ahuja (2015).

Knowledge Management practices (KM) is a means to pact with accomplishing authoritative goals by utilizing information, or "doing what is expected to benefit from learning assets. Skyrme (2001) characterizes learning the executives as "the unequivocal and efficient administration of indispensable information and its related procedures of creation, association, dissemination, use, and misuse". In the developing economies, KM practices suppose to be a key job and have been generally used by numerous companies as a prominent among the most excellent methods for making progress in the information era Malone (2002). Studies did in the correspondence business have demonstrated that the absence of representative exhibition influences the correspondence procedure in the budgetary part of Pakistan. These issues have made it practically unthinkable for some correspondence administration to provide food for their workforce staff need, expertise and experience to do their objectives (Yang (2010), (Hemamalini Suresh, 2014) Nowduri and Al-Dossary (2012). What the potential reasons and the answers are for conquered the circumstance? In particular, the aim of this assessment is to experimentally inspect the impact of Knowledge management practices on Employee performance with mediation role of organizational culture in the financial institutions in Pakistan.

The current financial emergency of Pakistan necessitates that associations esteem its advantages/assets at exactly that point associations can accomplish an edge and can develop. Furthermore, among every other part, the prime division is a money related segment where the board of information is as critical as blood forever. Subsequently, the focal point of this examination is in the banking area of Pakistan. This exploration is mainly putting accentuation on the disclosure of those critical components which powerfully affect the executives of information inside the association. Along these lines, elements of worry in this article are information sharing practices, representative execution, and hierarchical components. Despite of several studies to find the relationship between KM practices and employee performance, very little concentration has been given to develop the mediating mechanism of organization culture model which is called as CVF model. I have used CVF model as theoretical lens for this lens, because this model is never be testify to determine the relationship between KM practices and employee performance. The CVF model is a prominent and most widely used model in respect of organizational culture research literature inquires about because of its unwavering quality and viability.

Why measure employee performance of banking sector

Execution of workers of an association is a key worry of administrators independent of their dimension and position (Dhammike, 2013). Estimating worker work execution to ceaselessly improve qualities to work of employees and outcome is a key portion of the exhibition the board audit procedure. Routinely measurements integrate effectiveness, quality in work, devotion to institute esteems, and cooperation. Representative execution generally alludes to the measure of yield created from occupation execution by a worker over a specific timeframe in an association. The early origination of worker execution is to a great extent sponsored by logical administration. Thought concerned just the amount of yield of carrying out a responsibility. Nonetheless, the components of both amount and quality were added to the worker execution later in evaluating the execution of representatives. Productivity, adequacy, and quality were recognized as the real components of the representative exhibition (Lee, Lian, and Chen, 1999), which got much acknowledgment among scientists. Productivity alludes to the rate of yield on employment execution and furthermore complying with the time constraints for completing occupation errands. Adequacy, then again, speaks to the objective achievement rate by a specific worker. Specialists have used different techniques for estimating work execution and discovered different elements of it (Luo, Shi, Li, and Miao, 2008) since worker execution is said to be a multidimensional build (Befort and Hatstrup, 2003). This has actuated both specialist and analysts to distinguish the components of worker execution with the point of overseeing representative execution in associations. Thought the builds of representative presentation have been analyzed widely in the board writing (Borman, et. al, 1999), various thoughts on the originations of execution can be recognizable. One of the real concerns is to the estimation of individual work execution in hierarchical research (Bennett, Lance, and Wochr, 2014).

Worker execution in associations has found to have huge ramifications for the general execution of the association and its adequacy independent of their tendency. In spite of the fact that presentation is viewed as a total idea, specialists have recognized measurements related with it and thought of it as a multidimensional develop (Shaw, Delery, and Abdulla, 2003). A number of estimation models of worker execution have been created and tried in the field of the board over the previous decades (Motowidlo and Van Scotter, 1994). Notwithstanding, utilizing a proper model for estimating the presentation depending on the setting is a requirement for a powerful exhibition the board framework.

Competing Values Framework

Quinn and Rohrbaugh in 1983 determined the CVF model of organization culture by investigative the relationship between Campbell's (1977) adequacy criteria. In two section think about, both requested that seven scholastic specialists assess and one of Campbell's 30 adequacy criteria were applicable for organizational culture viability and examined reactions with multidimensional scale. Results uncovered that a three dimensional symmetrical arrangement was the most excellent depiction of these viability criterion. These three

fundamental dimensions, which were alluded to the center, arrangement, and means closes, were planned to speak to contending basic beliefs that "speak to what individuals esteem about an association's exhibition" (Cameron and Quinn, 1999). The formation of the CVF Figure below delineates that the elements of center and arrangement overlay to characterize the four social sorts including the CVF: tribe, adhocracy, market, and progression. The center measurement (even hub in Figure below) separates adequacy criteria that underline inside capacities, joining, and solidarity of procedures from those that middle on an outside direction and separation. The structure measurement (vertical pivot in Figure below) separates adequacy criterion that attention on adaptability and circumspection from criteria that underline dependability and control. The CVF's third model worth measurement implies closes, is the hypothetical premise whereupon the CVF designers elucidate why each culture type is related to a particular key push and a remarkable arrangement of viability criteria. Specifically, the third measurement clarifies the practices that radiate from qualities and convictions. These practices are the components (implies) through which culture types are connected with wanted viability criteria (closes). Expressed in an unexpected way, an aggregate's qualities and convictions are the social standardizing desires that illuminate individuals how they should carry on (Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; O' Reilly, Chatman, and Caldwell, 1991). Practices (taking an interest, going out on a limb, being forceful, holding fast to rules) consequently influence representatives' demeanors and substantial work yield. Delineates the essential presumptions, convictions, qualities, and ancient rarities basic each social sort alongside the adequacy criteria anticipated to identify with each kind. Since adequacy criteria are connected, recollect that culture types are bound to have fluctuating associations with viability criterion rather than inverse connections, as one would expect if the social kinds were genuinely dichotomous.

Problem Statement

KM is similarly essential and significant for banks all things considered for different establishments and associations. But there is thirst in literature to have research on knowledge management practices and its significance in improving the employee performance of banking sector. Despite of several studies to find the relationship between KM practices and employee performance, very little concentration has been given to develop the mediating mechanism of organization culture.

A small number of examinations relating mediating impact of organization culture with and KM were led with noteworthy outcomes. A few variables considered in these examinations incorporate, Critical achievement (Akhavan, Mostafa and Mohammad 2006) and advancement (Darroch, and McNaughton, 2015), Job Satisfaction Odembo (2013). Remaining Competitive Leng, and Shepherdson, (2012), are empowering influences, procedures, Lee and Choi, (2013), the frame of mind Liaw, Chen, G., and Huang, (2008). Value creation Kodama, (2016), Knowledge sharing Hansen, mors& Lovas (2016), Bhatti, and Qureshi, (2007). Al-Faris, Suliman (2010). The disappointment of numerous information sharing activities is regularly a consequence of social factors as opposed to innovative oversights. In such cases, authoritative culture can either encourage or block learning sharing exercises. However, it is, for the most part, accepted to be a principal hindrance to learning sharing (Grover and Davenport, 2001)

Knowledge practices is known to have gotten a significant measure of research enthusiasm crosswise over various hierarchical criteria Goh, A. (2016), Groff and Jones (2013), Gourlay, (2014). Giovanni (2012), Garud, and Kumaraswamy,(2016), Fahey, Srrivastava, Sharon, and Smith, (2014), Emadzade, Mashayekhi, and Abdar, (2012), Davenport, and Prusak, L (2008), Darr. also, Kurtz erg, (2012) Bose, R. (2016) Bock. and Gulkim, (2015)". Past examinations that endeavored to research on the impact of learning the board on representative presentation incorporate, The Role of information the executives in expanding execution proficiency in Damascus University (2010).

Hence, to investigating this gap this research will look at the impact of Knowledge management practices on the employee performance with mediation of organization culture prevails in banking sector of Pakistan.

Research question

This study will examine the impact of Knowledge creation and Knowledge application on Employee Performance (i.e. employee satisfaction and employee motivation), secondly this study will investigate the relationship between organizational culture dimensions (i.e. adhocracy culture and market culture) and employee performance (i.e. Employee motivation and employee satisfaction). Lastly this study will investigate how organization culture dimensions (i.e. adhocracy culture and market culture) mediate the relationship between knowledge management practices (i.e., Knowledge creation and Knowledge application) and employee performance (i.e. Employee motivation and employee satisfaction). Knowledge management practices help the Policymaker and administrator to improve performance of employees in the banking sector of Pakistan.

The following are the research questions of this study:

Do market and adhocracy cultures mediate the relationship between knowledge application, creation and performance of employees?

The objective of the study

The purpose of this research is:

- To investigating the organizational culture mediate role in between KM practices and performance of employees in the banking sector of Pakistan.
- To investigating the role of Organization Culture dimensions between the relationship of KM practices and performance of employees in the banking sector of Pakistan.
- To facilitate the banking expert and administrator to make necessary steps for improvement of performance of employees in the banking sector of Pakistan.
- To help the policymaker and Practitioners for making better policies to enhance performance of employees in the banking sector.
- To contribute in the existing literature by investigative the significance of KM practices on performance of employees with mediation role of organizational culture theory.

Theoretical and practical significance

The KM practices and procedure accentuates learning as creature made, communal and connected through relational communal connections in addition to suitable organization culture and employee performance. Hence, learning of how to advocate a steady organization culture that urges representatives to have the expectation to guarantee that information is made, put away, moved and connected is fundamental (Kayyworth and Leidner, 2003; Leidner and Kayyworth, 2006; Ajmal and Koskinen, 2008). So the finding of this study clearly contributes that organization culture model mediation enhance the knowledge management practices and employee performance. The Banking area is a strong spine for fund in the nation; the investigation of learning the executives is wanted to be significant to build the information and abilities of representative execution while carrying out the responsibility Yang (2011), a few examinations directed with regards to Knowledge the board and employee performance were done on private associations other than people in general. For instance, the Role of learning the board in expanding execution proficiency in University (2010), area. Learning the employee performance utilizes a mixture of procedures from Knowledge management practices give framework plan, for example, organized knowledge acquisition methodologies from topic specialists (McGraw and Harrison-Briggs 2019) of this examination will be led betterment with regards to the banking industry. This examination will likewise be noteworthy in a viable sense; the investigation will, for the most part, be of significance to the financial area in Pakistan. The investigation will give information that might be of advantage to worker execution in the financial business, on the most proficient method to improve representative execution inside the circle or authoritative culture as the capacity to form hierarchical culture is the vital significance in encouraging knowledge situations (Wei, 2015). Discoveries of this investigation will give headings and indications to learning acquisition; information sharing, information move, information usage, advancement, preparing programs, strategies; the board projects and the board improvement projects to the worker that will help guarantee representative execution inside the financial business. The state bank of Pakistan is regulator of all banks in Pakistan, all public and private banks have to follow the instruction of SBP, so this research suggest the SBP the significance and importance of KM practices in banking sector, in this era the banking sector has to face a lot of competition. The performance of each bank depends upon the performance of his employee as he banking sector is belong to service. This study will help the SBP to make the initiative to promote KM practices in banking sector to enhance the performance of employees. This study will also help the policy makers of each bank to promote KM practice in each bank to get the competitive edge. In the previous literature different indicators testify to enhance to employee performance but this will first detail study is conducted by using CVF model as theoretical lens with the implication of KM practices to enhance performance of employees.

Delimitations

The Scope endeavors to explore the impact of information the executives on representative presentation in the banking area in Pakistan. The investigation covers two aspects to be specific the free factor (representative execution) and the needy variable (learning the executives). Explicitly this examination explores ten banks in Pakistan. These banks would be considered as a component of the unit of investigation for this examination. It will likewise consider the changing pattern of information the executives its jobs, application on representative execution and furthermore it will quantify the progressions inside its rivals. The data is collected through online surveys from employees on banks in different province; the employees of same sector may have positive attitude, knowledge and beliefs. All variables data is collected from employees of same sector so it may enhance the chances of manipulated responses which considered as limitation of this research. Although different measures is taken to overcome this limitation and data is collected from all the provinces of Pakistan.

Literature review

Pakistan is a farming republic; its fundamental fares comprise of agrarian yields (for example sugar, cotton, rice and materials). Literacy rate in Pakistan is approximately 58% (Rehman, Jingdong & Hussain, 2015). The national language of Pakistan is Urdu while English is used as language for education, exchange, and other secretarial undertakings. Pakistan was home to the most prompt human progress in the area of South Asia, including Indus Valley and Gandhara development. Pakistan is viewed as the second most crowded Muslim nation on the planet, and is the announced sole atomic power in the Muslim World which encourages it to assume a significant place on the region.

Knowledge management practices and banking sector of Pakistan

First formal beginning of banking in Pakistan took place during the time of British imperialism (Goel & Manrai, 2016). After the freedom from British imperialism in 1947, extent of Pakistan is constitutively expanding. State Bank of Pakistan is pioneer of banks of Pakistan and it can also be termed as national bank of the country. According to State Bank of Pakistan information, there are 50.565 million financial balances in Pakistan, giving an infiltration rate of 24.34%. What's more, there are 15,053 bank offices, 14,148 ATMs, and 53,269 POS machines dynamic in the nation (State Bank of Pakistan, 2018).

As indicated by the Pakistan Federal Bureau of Revenue (FBR), out of the majority of the budgetary administrations in the nation, the financial business sits at the center of the money related part. It was privatized in the mid-1990s, because of the poor execution of national banks (Pakistan Federal Bureau of Revenue Report, 2015), and this activated remote interest in the business. The financial framework in Pakistan is sorted in the accompanying way: Shah et al. (2014) researched the learning the board rehearses in the client administration and loaning divisions of one of Bulgaria's top retail banks and revealed how KM procedures can be additionally improved. Despite the fact that basics of learning sharing are clear from the KM exercises in various divisions of the bank, the restrictions, for example, protection from change of the executed KM frameworks are blocking the viability of the information the executive's procedure. Additional preparation and motivating forces are expected to build learning creation and sharing. Besides, a plainly verbalized KM technique alongside progress criteria and duty and backing from senior administration is required. There was an extreme absence of information the board ponders in Bulgarian setting by and large and Bulgarian financial area specifically.

Knowledge management practices, organization culture and employee performance

Knowledge Management is an amazing, multidisciplinary, and controversial idea. Learning Management empowers the current individual knowledge to be caught and changed into hierarchical information, which in turn must be diffused and shared by numerous workers. These workers use this knowledge however they likewise make new person, which ends up hierarchical, and so on. Learning Management is likewise the administration of organization's knowledge that can improve numerous highlights of hierarchical execution in order to be increasingly "canny acting" (Gupta, Iyer, and Aronson, 2012). In his paper (Bray, 2013) has recognized and looked into four points of view inside the writing encompassing learning the executives (KM) inquire about at the authoritative dimension: data frameworks, the executives, hierarchical learning, and methodology viewpoints. The present investigation is worried about the data frameworks point of view. Alavi and Leidner's (2001) MIS Quarterly article speaks to the original audit piece on KM and information systems; regularly referred to in ensuing works. Their article outlines the learning based perspective on the firm, broadening prior research by Nonaka (1994), and Grant (1996), and Argote and Ingram (2000) around there. In particular, Alavi and Leidner (2001) recommend that learning speaks to data had in the brains of people, explicitly "customized data (which could possibly be new, one of a kind, helpful, or exact) identified with certainties, methods, ideas, translations, thoughts, perceptions, and decisions." Their audit article proposes other elective portrayals of learning also, to incorporate information as speaking to a perspective, object, process, access to data, or an ability. For each situation, data frameworks assume jobs in supporting the "administration" of learning. An information sharing society in an association that is gravely job displayed by those most astounding in the association's progression can impede learning the board. High positioning staff may believe themselves to could easily compare to other people showing in not sharing information. Progressively organized associations have all the earmarks of being the standard in southern Africa, Grant (2006).

Information creation (KC) is considered as particular dimension of learning (Lyles, 2013). The age of new information or learning creation happens utilizing four techniques for the Socialization, Externalization, Combination and Internalization (SECI) strategy to improve better execution. Affiliations should attempt insightful undertakings to look for and portray material information and its sources from both inside and outside the affiliation (Lawson, 2003). Learning creation construes the ability to make information and hover it in the things, organizations, and structures, and the whole relationship for better execution (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Learning application is a strategy whereby information is accessible and is utilized for basic leadership purposes and passing on guidelines to people who don't have the learning or at the end of the day that a person who has learning guides another. Information application is the use of learning established in methodology, decides and forms that immediate future exhibition. KA is a static method of acclimatizing and sorting out learning into an association's items or administrations (Li, 2007). Learning application accept the mix of information from evident sources to make dynamic limit working through instruments in context of guidelines or decision making conditions (Grant, 1996). Information applications utilized in a favorable manner towards improve authoritative execution (Olsen and Tobiassen, 2011). Performance is the final product of exercises; it incorporates the genuine results of the vital management process (Alrubaiee, 2012). In like manner Ben Zaied et al., (2015) placed that the hierarchical exhibition is represented by the achievement in accomplishing its objectives. Hierarchical execution establishes all behaviors related to authoritative destinations relying upon the commitment levels of individuals to the association (Borman and Motowidlo, 2013). In the organizational context, performance is typically characterized as the degree to which a hierarchical part adds to accomplishing

the objectives of the association. Representatives are an essential wellspring of upper hand in administration situated associations (Luthans and Stajkovic, (2009); Pfeffer, (2016). What's more, a dedication execution approach sees workers as assets or resources, and qualities their voice. Worker execution assumes a significant job for hierarchical execution. Representative execution is initially what a worker does or does not do. Execution of representatives could include: amount of yield, nature of yield, practicality of yield, nearness at work, helpfulness (Güngör, 2011). Reviewing the specific impact of each KM system uninhibitedly has not been addressed adequately. Looking at the activities required for the methodical treatment of learning resources is fundamental [Heisig, 2009]. Relating KM and business techniques is an essential accomplishment factor for KM and for incredible usage of corporate portal [Benbya et al., 2004]. Likewise, laborers' clear KMS focal points are an imperative determinant of their usage [Wu and Wang, 2006; Becerra-Fernandez et al., 2004]. By and large, the connection between adhocracy societies and representative frames of mind should be more negative than that between group societies and worker mentalities on the grounds that the impacts of an adhocracy culture don't straightforwardly impact aggregate representative dispositions. Similarly as with adhocracy societies, contradicting instruments may weaken the greatness of the connection between market societies and representative mentalities. Market societies cultivate positive aggregate representative frames of mind when units accomplish objectives. Gathering individuals get fulfillment from accomplishing objectives on the grounds that the way of life gives significant extraneous and additionally inherent prizes (Judge, Bono, Erez, and Locke, 2005; Maier and Brunstein, 2001).

Research Model

Research Methodology

Qualitative and quantitative research methods are foremost methods used in social sciences, According to Cresswell (2013), quantitative and qualitative research methods are used in social sciences research but new emerging approach, used in current time is mixed research method. The quantitative research comprises the collection of data through surveys and investigation of data with numbers and examination of variables and their relation in a specific environment. According to Ary, Jacobs, Sornsen and walker 2013, the quantitative research divided into two forms, experimental and non experimental form. Experimental approach is a scientific and systematic method to investigation in which the variables manipulate with each other and investigate the change of variable or with each other variables. While in reverse the non experimental research approach is a scientific and systematic method to investigation in which there is lack of variables manipulate with each other and investigate the change of variable or with each other variables Serkaran (2006). The survey method is most used research techniques for non experimental research, in survey method the instrument is distributed among respondent and their views are investigated with different statistical tools Ary (2013).

The study will be aimed at drawing samples from banks in Pakistan. Therefore there is a need for simple random sampling. According to SBP June Publication of scheduled bank report 2018, the total numbers of working employees in banking industry of Pakistan are 73431. There are several techniques in determining the sample size. Krejcie and morgan (1970), Scentific approach will be used for this study. The both give general guideline for the selection of sample hence there is no need of calculation. So for the adopting the model of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) technique for the study there is no requirement for the calculation, their suggested table is for the selection of sample according to population is enough for selection. According to Krejcie and morgan table, the sample size 382 is appropriate for the population 75000. The sample size of 382 is the representation of the whole population if we take margin of 0.05 chances of error and 95% of the confidence. For the better result the research add 48 samples then the total sample is 430.

By considering 73431 employees in all banking sector of Pakistan, I apply formula provided by Yamane (1967) to draw minimum sample, which is as follows:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Where:

- n = the sample size
- N = the population of the study
- e = level of significance (0.05 set in current research)

To arrive at sample size the above formula is used to attain minimum quantities as follows:

$$n = 73431 / (1 + 73431 \cdot [(0.05)]^2)$$

$$n = 73431 / (1 + (73431 \times 0.0025))$$

$$n = 73431 / (1 + (183.5775))$$

$$n = 73431 / 184.5775$$

n=398

And, in second part we consider the population as lowest number of employees in one bank, one major government bank is national bank whose employees are 9862 then by applying the same formula provided by Yamane (1967) to draw minimum limit for sample:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

$$n = 9862 / (1 + 9862 \cdot [(0.05)]^2)$$

$$n = 9862 / (1 + (9862 \times 0.0025))$$

$$n = 9862 / (1 + (24.655))$$

$$n = 9862 / 25.655$$

$$n = 384$$

According to calculation the higher sample is 398 and lower sample is 384 and if we take average of sample the result is 391. The sample size of 391 is the representation of the whole population if we take margin of 0.05 chances of error and 95% of the confidence. For the better result the research add 39 samples then the total sample is 430. According to Ary (2013) if the sample size increases so the sample error can automatically decrease. According to Joseph Hair, Babin, Black, Anderson and Tatham in 2006 suggested that sample size can be select with the items of the variables. It must be larger than five times of the items of observations. In this study the items of observations is 58 so it multiply to five, the result is 290, so according to them the 290 sample is enough for this study and the research take 430 sample, it will reduce the chances of errors. The 290 sample size is enough for the study Joseph Hair (2006). The above calculations and researchers recommendations shows 430 sample is good for this study as it reduce the chances of error and increase the level of confidence.

Question format

Survey instrument comprises three parts. Part (a) consists fifteen items Turyasingura, W., (2011) associated to KM practices. Part (b) contains eight items Saeed Sadighi 2017 related to organization culture. Part (c) has twelve items Shafizal Mat Loughborough University Institutional Repository 2016 related to employee performance. Part (d) has nine items related to demographic factors. In total the questionnaire comprised fifty-four items in four parts. The instrument all questions are close ended. As explained by Roszkowski and Bean (1990) and Yammarino et al. (1991), it is necessary to maintain conciseness and relevancy in the questions to get desired results. To get maximum output, researcher used a self-administrative survey in which the researcher read the statement and elaborated it (where necessary) to the respondent and completed the questionnaire based on the feedback of the respondent. With this method, in a situation where the respondent gave non-serious or biased feedback, the researcher mentioned it in a comment on the questionnaire and later that questionnaire was excluded from the study. There were items in the questionnaire that were constituent of specific variables; for example, there were five items in the questionnaire to elaborate classical leadership. As narrated by Stangor (1998), in order to elaborate a variable, multiple items are used. In order to get the appropriate results, researcher needed to take an average result of the items.

Research Analysis

3.10.2. Descriptive Statistics of Questioner Items

The questionnaire of this study contains 6 variables and data was gathered for the study analysis, the below table give the average response of respondents, Knowledge Application, Knowledge Creation and second two types of culture, adhocracy, and market. The last two variables relate to employee performance; Employee motivation and Employee Satisfaction. The total numbers of 35 questions were used for the analysis of this study.

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
KA1	40	1	5	3.712	0.80543
KA2	40	1	5	3.595	0.87385
KA3	40	1	5	3.843	0.80778
KA4	40	1	5	3.749	0.81774
KA5	40	1	5	3.828	0.74681
KA6	40	1	5	3.858	0.72637
KA7	40	1	5	3.825	0.72784
KA8	40	1	5	3.674	0.86961
KC1	40	1	5	3.751	0.78798
KC2	40	1	5	3.658	0.87005
KC3	40	1	5	3.628	0.77319
KC4	40	1	5	3.258	0.80219
KC5	40	1	5	3.638	0.85809

CA1	40	1	5	2.602	0.98117
CA2	40	1	5	3.865	0.59559
CA3	40	1	5	3.731	0.82883
CA4	40	1	5	3.744	0.76011
CM1	40	1	5	3.842	0.69505
CM2	40	1	5	3.886	0.67146
CM3	40	2	5	3.888	0.74584
CM4	40	2	5	3.888	0.65605
EM1	40	1	5	3.416	0.90645
EM2	40	1	5	3.614	0.91595
EM3	40	2	5	3.598	0.82985
EM4	40	2	5	3.707	0.81504
EM5	40	1	5	3.661	0.80850
EM6	40	2	5	3.974	0.73017
EM7	40	2	5	3.751	0.80264
ES1	40	1	5	3.225	0.98822
ES2	40	1	5	3.125	1.04677
ES3	40	1	5	3.354	0.87304
ES4	40	1	5	3.256	0.87849
ES5	40	1	5	3.745	0.82052
ES6	40	1	5	3.125	0.76508
ES7	40	1	5	3.328	0.85625

External Factor Loading

According to Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt (2016), 0.70 value of external loading of each item is good for data and the value of external loading is show there is no error contain in data and not fit for further analysis if the over 0.70.

	CA	CM	EM	ES	KA	KC
CA1	0.812					
CA2	0.765					
CA3	0.823					
CA4	0.726					
CM1		0.876				
CM2		0.902				
CM3		0.860				
CM4		0.756				
EM1			0.845			
EM2			0.852			
EM3			0.897			
EM4			0.924			
EM5			0.877			
EM6			0.709			
EM7			0.918			
ES1				0.736		
ES2				0.898		
ES3				0.718		
ES4				0.769		

ES5	0.766
ES6	0.725
ES7	0.831
KA1	0.891
KA2	0.849
KA3	0.795
KA4	0.876
KA5	0.758
KA6	0.852
KA7	0.950
KA8	0.814
KC1	0.822
KC2	0.775
KC3	0.812
KC4	0.748
KC5	0.841
KC6	0.754
KC7	0.803

Average Variance Extracted

The convergent validity is average variance extracted at each item level of the instrument. According to Hair et al., (2016) the average variance extracted is equal to the squared loading total divided into the item of each construct. When the value of average variance extracted is at least 0.5 then it is sufficient to meet construct validity.

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CA	0.712	0.751	0.700
CM	0.919	0.836	0.685
EM	0.925	0.831	0.760
ES	0.809	0.827	0.746
KA	0.768	0.797	0.623
KC	0.751	0.787	0.829

Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

The third part of discriminant validity examination is Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), According to Henseler (2015), this method is calculate the correlation among different constructs and identified that the relationship among different constructs in normal and valid for analysis. According to Kline (2015), the value of correlation among constructs must be lower than 0.85 for valid Discriminant validity.

	CA	CM	EM	ES	KA	KC
Adhocracy Culture						
Market culture	0.702					
Employee Motivation	0.860	0.715				
Employee Satisfaction	0.783	0.617	0.701			
Knowledge Application	0.812	0.751	0.885	0.767		
Knowledge Creation	0.812	0.768	0.845	0.779	0.791	

Summary of Measurement model

Structural Model

Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Knowledge Application -> Adhocracy Culture -> Employee Motivation	0.191	0.191	0.059	3.211	0.001
Knowledge Creation -> Adhocracy Culture -> Employee Motivation	0.197	0.198	0.063	3.133	0.002
Knowledge Application -> Market Culture -> Employee Satisfaction	0.156	0.159	0.059	2.649	0.008

Application -> Market Culture -> Employee Motivation					
Knowledge Creation -> Market Culture -> Employee Motivation	0.302	0.298	0.069	4.351	0.000
Knowledge Application -> Adhocracy Culture -> Employee Satisfaction	0.160	0.159	0.067	2.406	0.016
Knowledge Creation -> Adhocracy Culture -> Employee Satisfaction	0.166	0.165	0.071	2.320	0.020
Knowledge Application -> Market Culture -> Employee Satisfaction	0.173	0.179	0.071	2.449	0.014
Knowledge Creation -> Market Culture -> Employee Satisfaction	0.334	0.330	0.080	4.174	0.000

The above table shows the finding of mediate effect of adhocracy and market Culture between satisfaction & motivation of employees and knowledge application & knowledge creation, the findings express that adhocracy and market culture has statistically positive and significant mediate relationship between satisfaction & motivation of employees and knowledge application & creation. According to Joseph F Hair (2016), if the value of P is less than 0.05 and value of T is more than 2 then there is positive relationship between the variable, The above table shows the value of P is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2 so it shows there is significant and positive mediation between the variables.

Discussion on results

Knowledge Management (KM) has advanced from a rising idea to an inexorably regular capacity in business associations. It is an open mystery that banking has changed over into the matter of data from the financial matters (Dzinkowski, 2019). The information based hypothesis of the association expresses that extreme intensity does not get through the making of new learning instead of the application and sharing of the information (Akran and Hilman, 2018) and positive organizational culture (Rabelo, Oliveira, and Viena, 2015). The primary target of this examination is to direct quantitative research to have the option to make a more extensive arrangement of proof with respect to the connection among KM and authoritative execution having market and adhocracy culture as interceding factor and impact of employee performance. This research is conducted on employees of banking industry of Pakistan, in this research KM practices takes as independent variable which has two dimensions (Knowledge Application, Knowledge Creation) and mediate as organization culture which has two dimensions (Adhocracy and Market culture) and the dependent variable as employee performance which has two dimensions (employee motivation and employee satisfaction). The present research will survey the impact of KM practices on performance of employees will be checked through the interceding impact of organizational culture following the CVF hypothesis. The finding of this mediating hypothesis is presented in last part and in this section the investigator is talk about the findings and the interpretation of the results.

The hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of Adhocracy Culture between motivation of employees and knowledge application, the conclusion express that Adhocracy culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between motivation of employees and knowledge application. The P value is equal to 0.00 and T value is larger than 2. The finding of this is same in some past studies which conducted on knowledge

management practices, employee performance and organization culture. Franco, M., Lucianetti, L., & Bourne, M. (2012) conduct a detailed study on organization culture deminsions and their impact on employee performance and found positive relationship. Imran, M. K., Ilyas, M., Aslam, U., & Fatima, T. (2018) conduct study on performance of education sectors and they found employee creativity enhance with the implementation of knowledge process. The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of Adhocracy Culture between satisfaction of employees and knowledge application, the findings express that Adhocracy culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between satisfaction of employees and knowledge application. The value of P is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2. The finding of this is same in some past studies which conducted on KM practices, performance of employees and organization culture. Goel, U., & Manrai, R. (2016, March) conduct his study on banking sector and found with the augmentation of knowledge economy the performance of employees are also enhanced and if the organization culture is also adaptive. Bavik, Tang & Shao (2018) found positive relationship between satisfaction of employees and knowledge application.

The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of Adhocracy Culture between motivation of employees and knowledge creation, the findings express that Adhocracy culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between motivation of employees and knowledge creation. The value of P is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2. Heisig (2009) had outlined and examined about 160 frameworks of KM practices and analyzed demonstrated that the majority types of KM practices are illustrious, make, store, share, and create learning have positive relation with employee motivation. Wiig (2016) suggested that KM practices are a gathering of clearly defined procedure or techniques used to look through significant information among different culture that enhance the board tasks. The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of Adhocracy Culture between satisfaction of employees and knowledge creation, the findings express that Adhocracy culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between satisfaction of employees and knowledge creation. The value of P is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2. Arthur Anderson Business Consulting (2009) believed that employees and innovate culture are the greatest empowering agents of management execution. Swart et al. (2016) employee satisfaction done because of knowledge creation preparing program which improve employees inspiration and their working ability. The company increases the creative activities, the employee will happier, so it increases the firm profit and efficiency. (Champathes, 2006).

The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of market Culture between motivation of employees and knowledge application, the findings express that market culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between motivation of employees and knowledge application. The value of P is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2. The finding of this is same in some past studies which conducted on knowledge management practices, employee performance and organization culture. Alharbi, M. F. (2012) found in his study the organization culture has mediate effect between KM practices and performance. Aledwan, B. (2014) conducts his study on banking sectore and found mediation of organization culture for employee motivation. The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of market Culture between knowledge application and employee satisfaction, the findings express that market culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between knowledge application and employee satisfaction. The Value of P is equal to 0.00 and Value of T is larger than 2. The finding of this is same in some past studies which conducted on knowledge management practices, employee performance and organization culture. Alharbi, M. F. (2012) found in his study the organization culture has mediate effect between KM practices and performance. Aledwan, B. (2014) conduct his study on banking sectore and found mediation of organization culture for employee motivation.

The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of market Culture between motivation of employees and knowledge creation, the conclusion express that market culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between knowledge creation and employee motivation. The value of P is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2. Arthur Anderson Business Consulting (2009) accepted that people, corporate culture and data innovation are the greatest empowering agents of knowledge management execution, knowledge creation is the reason to motivate the employees. Swart et al. (2016) employee performance execution happen simply because of good quality knowledge creation preparing program that prompts worker inspiration and their needs fulfilment. More the created workers, more they are happy with their activity, henceforth expanding the firm efficiency and gainfulness. (Champathes, 2006). The next hypothesis is developed to find mediate effect of market Culture between satisfaction of employee and knowledge creation, the conclusion express that market culture has statistically significant and positive mediate relationship between satisfaction of employees and knowledge creation. The value of p is equal to 0.00 and value of T is larger than 2. Swart et al. (2016) employee performance is excellent due to good quality and knowledge creation programs gives the inspiration to employees for their need fulfillment. As the workers are more created, they are happier with their activities and firm efficiency improved and they earn more. (Champathes, 2006).

Conclusion

The result explains that there is positive and direct mediation of organization culture (adhocracy, market culture) between KM practices (knowledge application, knowledge creation) and employee performance (employee motivation and satisfaction). All the mediation shows positive and direct relationship between the KM practices and performance of employees. KM practices is known to have gotten a significant measure of research enthusiasm crosswise over various culture criteria Goh, A. (2016), Groff and Jones(2013), Gourlay, (2014). Giovanni (2012), Garud, and Kumaraswamy,(2016), Fahey, Srrivastava, Sharon, and Smith, (2014), Emadzade, Mashayekhi, and Abdar, (2012), Davenport, and Prusak, L (2008), Darr. also, Kurtz erg, (2012) Bose, R. (2016) Bock. and Gulkim, (2015)". Past examinations that endeavored to research on the impact of KM practices the board on representative presentation incorporate culture, Damascus University (2010).

Further Remaining Competitive Leng, and Shepherdson, (2012), are knowledge management practices, procedures, Lee and Choi, (2013), the frame of mind Liaw, Chen, G., and Huang, (2008). Value creation Kodama, (2016), Knowledge sharing Hansen, mors& Lovas (2016), Bhatti, and Qureshi, (2007), Al-Faris, Suliman, (2010) found positive relation between KM practices and performance of employees. The finding of this study in some past studies which conducted on KM practices, performance of employees and organization culture. According to Abualoush, S. H., Obeidat, A. M., Tarhini, A., Masa'deh, R. E., & Al-Badi, A. (2018) with implementation of knowledge management practices the employee performance enhances. As per saeed saidgi (2017) the organization culture has significant relationship with employee performance.

There is thrust in literature no study is conducted which conduct on CVF model mediation between KM practices and performance of employees. The result of this study is also addition in literature; this study finds mediation of organization culture between all dimensions of KM practices and performance of employees. This study recommend that within all organization culture prevails in banking industry of Pakistan, the management implement the knowledge practices so this can increase the employee motivation and satisfaction and increase the bank productivity.

Recommendations

This research is purely conducted on Banking sector but the scope of KM practices can be evaluated in different sector of Pakistan, due to time and resources constrain the researcher is only consider one sector so it is further recommended this study can be conducted on different sectors which results can enhance the performance of employees. The instrument of this research in adapted from different studies and validated through different statistical techniques so it recommended the validity of instrument can be upgraded and with implementation of additional KM practices different phenomena can be testified and contributes in literature as well policy implementations.

The data is gathered through online surveys and quantitative technique is used to testify the CVF theoretical lens but it is further recommended in depth interviews can be conducted on executive level to implement the KM practices and to evaluate the performance of employee so qualitative study is recommended for future study. There is thrust in literature CVF model of organization culture is not testified by implementing KM practices to evaluate performance of employees in banking industry of Pakistan. This study gives detail investigation of this issue so it is further recommended that this theoretical lens can be testify to evaluate the organizational performance and efficiency.

This research identifies the mediate effect of organization culture between KM practices and performance of employees, there are two performance indicator are taken for analysis satisfaction and motivation due to time and resources constraint but in literature different indicators of performance are taken by researcher so CVF lens can be evaluated with different employee performance indicators. This research is conducted on specific sector and culture, to overcome the specification issue this research can be conducted in future with more generally like with change of demographic, change of culture and sector, this CVF model can be testify with more generally.

This research is conducted on KM practices implementation on banking industry to check the performance of employees, the KM practices is detailed phenomena in literature so it is further recommended the each KM practices e.g Knowledge sharing tools can be testify with same CVF model and performance of employees. Data is collected of all variables with same population and items of measurement is adapted with limitation, the future recommendations is this model can be testify with additional measurement of items and data can be collected of all variables with different population it might result of different findings.

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